

Human and Machine Performance in Counting Sound Classes in Single-Channel Soundscapes

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Individual sounds are difficult to detect in complex soundscapes due to a strong overlap. This article explores the task of estimating sound polyphony, which is defined here as the number of audible sound classes. Sound polyphony measures the complexity of a soundscape and can be used to inform sound classification algorithms. We first perform a listening test to assess the difficulty of the task. The results show that humans are only able to reliably count up to three simultaneous sound sources and that they underestimate the degree of polyphony for more complex soundscapes. Human performance depends mainly on the spectral characteristics of the sounds, and in particular on the number of overlapping noise-like and transient sounds. In a second step, we compare four deep neural network architectures, including an object detection approach for natural images, to contrast human performance with machine learning-based approaches. The results show that machine listening systems can outperform human listeners for the task at hand. Based on our results, an implicit modelling of the sound polyphony based on the number of previously detected sound classes seems less promising than the explicit modelling strategy.

0 Introduction

Our auditory system shows its impressive capabilities when we listen to complex soundscapes, which range from scenarios with multiple active speakers (often referred to as cocktail party scenarios), to music ensembles with several instruments, to everyday soundscapes with multiple static and moving sound sources. In many tasks such as audio source separation, speech recognition, and music transcription, algorithms benefit from prior information about the number of sound sources (sound polyphony).

In the auditory scene analysis model proposed by Bregman [1], the human auditory system groups audible sounds along frequency (simultaneous grouping) and time (sequential grouping). As a result of this grouping, sounds are either integrated into a single auditory perception, which is mentally assigned to a single sound source, or segregated into different auditory streams, which are assigned to individual sound sources. In dense soundscapes particularly, grouping errors can cause the auditory stream segregation to fail and overlapping sounds to be perceived as blended sounds, which complicates their classification.

The concept of polyphony can be interpreted from different perspectives and its estimation is addressed in various research tasks. In the music domain, polyphony denotes the

number of simultaneously sounding pitched sound events (tones) or temporal sequences thereof (melodic lines) [2]. A closely related task is music ensemble size estimation, which aims to estimate of the number of simultaneously active instruments [3]. In speech processing, a common task is to estimate the number of active speakers (speaker counting). In the computer vision domain, related research tasks are object counting [4] and face counting [5] in natural images.

In this study, we investigate the task of sound polyphony estimation (SPE) for everyday sounds. Salamon et al. define sound polyphony as the maximum number of overlapping sounds at any time in an audio recording [6]. As a disadvantage, this definition requires precise sound event annotations, which are ill-defined for sound classes with ambiguous start and end times. Therefore, we propose an alternative definition and measure sound polyphony as the number of unique sound classes audible in a short audio segment. This definition focuses on sound event tagging (SET), i. e., classifying audible sounds without precisely locating them. As an additional self-imposed constraint of this study, we restrict ourselves to single-channel audio recordings, suppressing the spatial perception of sound sources based on multi-channel information. Such single-

Fig. 1. Example of a polyphonic soundscape (USM evaluation set, 445.wav, sound polyphony degree of $y_p = 4$). Log-magnitude scaled Mel spectrograms are shown for the four underlying audio stems of the sound classes *truck*, *dogs*, *rain*, and *drilling* (middle and bottom rows, from left to right), as well as for the mixture (top left). The colored plot (top right) illustrates how sounds overlap in the time-frequency space.

microphone setup can be relevant for low-cost acoustic sensors.

As an introductory example, Figure 1 illustrates a five-second single-channel soundscape recording as Mel spectrogram (top left), which includes sound events from the four sound classes “truck” engine, “dog” barking, “rain” drops, and “drilling” (middle and bottom rows, from left to right). While each sound class shows distinctive spectral patterns, these patterns overlap as shown in the colored spectrogram plot (top right). We assign to this soundscape a polyphony degree of four even though some of the sound classes appear as multiple sound events.

As the main contributions of this study, we compare the human and machine performance for SPE based on single-channel audio recordings. We first present the results of a listening test and analyze in detail the human ability to count sound classes in polyphonic soundscapes. We then investigate the performance of several deep neural networks, which are trained to model SPE either explicitly or implicitly by first classifying active sound classes before counting them to compute the sound polyphony. The studied machine listening methods are based on Mel spectrogram input and include an adapted object detection algorithm, which is fine-tuned to recognize sound classes based on characteristic spectral patterns.

1 Related Work on Auditory Counting Tasks

1.1 Human Performance

Early psychoacoustic research involved listening tests based on simple stimuli, for example sinusoids and noise-like signals [7]. Natural audio signals such as speech, music, or everyday sounds are more complex in their spectral composition [8, 9, 10]. Despite their widely differing spectral properties, these signals are processed by the human auditory system using the same organizational principles [11]. The auditory perception of complex acoustic environments is challenging due to the unpredictable number of sound sources. At the same time, the number of auditory streams which humans can process simultaneously is limited to a maximum of four sources according to Kawashima et al. [12]. As a potential reason, Weisser [13] argues that the human auditory system gradually loses information during the processing of audio signals on the way from the ear periphery, stream formation, attention, to the final cognition step in order to avoid cognitive overflow and to better focus on particular sound sources.

Two studies investigated how our ability to recognize and annotate sound events is influenced by the number of concurrent sounds and their spectral characteristics. Carthwright et al. [14] showed that the human performance in annotating sound events decreases with increasing sound polyphony. As the main reason, the authors found that with more complex sound mixtures, humans tend to miss more and more relevant sound events (decreasing recall measure) while the annotation quality remains stable (stable precision measure). Piczak [15] found that the human sound event annotation performance is lower for noisy and ambient sounds and higher for more distinct sound sources as well as human and animal sounds. Given these results, we hypothesize that annotators tend to underestimate the sound polyphony degree in complex soundscapes and that the polyphony annotation performance is affected by the spectral characteristics of the audible sounds.

With a focus on music signals, Schöffler et al. [16] conducted a listening test on the task of counting musical instruments in short audio excerpts. Similar to our study, the stimuli covered polyphony degrees between one and six, which corresponds to one up to six different instruments per recording. The results showed that annotators could only reliably count up to three instruments. Similarly, humans can accurately segregate and count up to three simultaneous musical voices [17]. The performance decreases if the corresponding instrument timbres are more similar to each other [18].

1.2 Machine Performance

In this section, we will contrast the human performance on auditory counting tasks as discussed in the previous section with that of algorithms. Such algorithms often combine methods from audio signal processing and machine learning to estimate the number of sound sources.

In speech processing, the estimated number of speakers is often used to inform source separation algorithm in order to isolate each speaker signal. In contrast to natural sound-

scapes, the acoustic characteristics of different speakers can be very similar and therefore harder to distinguish. The number of speakers is commonly estimated explicitly using a multi-class classification approach [19, 20] based on deep neural networks or via clustering of sound sources in latent representation spaces [21, 22, 23].

The task of counting sound sources in soundscapes is commonly approached by analyzing multi-channel recordings. Several authors proposed methods for joint sound source counting, localization, and separation [24, 25, 26]. Since the spatial composition of a soundscape can be captured by the multi-channel recording setup, the number of (spatially distributed) sound sources can be estimated with high accuracy values of up to 89.8 % for six sound sources [25].

Multimodal approaches, which analyze both audio and visual data by learning joint representation spaces, exist for tasks such as crowd counting [27, 28] and repetition counting [29].

2 Task Definition

In this study, we represent a *soundscape recording* using a single-channel audio sample vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s}$ of N_s samples. A soundscape commonly includes multiple *sound events*, each associated to one of N_c *sound classes*. We define a sound class activity vector as $y_c \in \{0, 1\}^{N_c}$, which indicates whether at least one sound event in x is associated to the c -th sound class with $c \in [1, N_c]$. Further, we define the *sound polyphony degree* y_p and consider SPE as the task of learning the mapping

$$f_{\text{SPE}} : x \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s} \mapsto y_p \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (1)$$

As illustrated in Figure 2, we distinguish between *explicit* SPE and *implicit* SPE (as in [30]). While explicit SPE directly estimates y_p from x as in (1), implicit SPE first uses a (multi-label) SET model

$$f_{\text{SET}} : x \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s} \mapsto y_c \in \{0, 1\}^{N_c} \quad (2)$$

to estimate the sound class activity y_c for each of N_c sound classes based on the thresholded sigmoid layer output of f_{SET} . Then, y_p is simply estimated from the number of active classes using

$$y_p = \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} (y_c)_i. \quad (3)$$

As confirmed by the majority of our listening test participants (compare Section 4), human listeners tend to approach the SPE task in an implicit fashion, detecting sounds prior to counting them.

3 Dataset

A manual annotation of the temporal boundaries of sound events in polyphonic soundscapes is labor-intensive and often further complicated by the overlap of concurrent sound events. As a consequence, many academic datasets include artificially generated soundscape recordings, which can be created in abundance by randomly mix-

Fig. 2. SPE modeled explicitly using f_{SPE} (lower branch) or implicitly by counting the number of sound classes estimated by an SET model f_{SET} (upper branch).

ing multiple isolated sound recordings [6, 31, 20]. In this study, we use the publicly-available Urban Sound Monitoring (USM) dataset [32]¹, which includes 24,000 polyphonic soundscapes of five seconds duration. Every soundscape is created by mixing between one and six isolated sound recordings (*stems*) using random loudness ratios and spatial positions in a two-channel setup. A distinction is made between foreground and background sounds. Prior to the mixing, all stems are normalized to a perceived loudness of -12 dB LUFS based on ITU-R BS.1770-4 specification (see [32], Section 2.3 for details).

The dataset covers 26 sound classes for urban sound monitoring, including vehicle sounds, construction site sounds, human-made sounds, animal sounds, climate sounds, and rare sounds such as sirens, gunshots, and church bells.

In our experiments, we combine both stems ($y_p = 1$) and artificially mixed soundscapes ($y_p \in [2, 6]$) and consider a sound polyphony range between $y_p \in [1, 6]$. We adopt the pre-defined training/validation/test split of the USM dataset. As the only exception, we randomly sample a subset of the (monophonic) stems for $y_p = 1$ from the training and validation sets to keep the polyphony classes approximately balanced during training. For the final model evaluation, we consider all soundscapes of the evaluation set.

Two issues, which complicate the SPE task, need to be discussed. First, the USM soundscapes are composed of foreground sounds and background sounds whose loudness levels were randomly sampled from different value ranges (compare Section 2.3, [32]). Some background sounds, which have a mixing coefficient close to the lower limit of -20 dB, are probably difficult to hear. Furthermore, the USM dataset builds upon audio samples uploaded to the collaborative audio database FreeSound². Some of the audio examples exhibit unlabeled background noises in addition to the labeled sound events [33]. Such incomplete annotations can bias the human SPE performance since they increase the sound polyphony degree.

4 Human Performance

4.1 Listening Test

We conducted a listening test between November 2022 and January 2023 in a controlled lab environment to assess the human performance in SPE. Participants used closed

¹<https://github.com/jakobabesser/USM>

²<https://freesound.org/>

Fig. 3. Section of the graphical user interface of the listening test showing the Mel spectrogram of a test item. Participants are also presented with a list of all 26 sound classes of the USM dataset (not shown here).

headphones during the annotation and were guided through the listening test in a graphical interface displayed in a common web browser as illustrated in Figure 3. The listening test was implemented in a locally hosted website using Django, HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. The website was optimized and tested for different web browsers on a desktop computer.

4.2 Participants & Stimuli

In total, 24 participants took part in this experiment, all of whom indicated prior experience from other listening tests. The number of participants per age group are 3 (18 to 24 years), 12 (25 to 34 years), 6 (35 to 44 years), 2 (45 to 54 years), and 1 (older than 55 years). The participants included part of the scientific staff at Fraunhofer IDMT as well as students at the Technische Universität in Ilmenau, Germany. No material incentive was given to participants.

All audio clips were randomly selected from the USM evaluation set taking into account a balanced polyphony degree (compare Section 3). The two-channel soundscapes were down-mixed by averaging both audio channels in order to remove any spatial cues for sound localization. A subset of the listening test stimuli can be accessed on an accompanying website [34]. All participants used closed headphones (Beyerdynamic DT 770) and could adjust the volume at any time during the listening test.

4.3 Training Procedure

Before starting the experiment, each participant underwent two voluntary training steps to familiarize themselves with the audio material and the annotation task. In the first step, participants could listen to 11 random sound stems from each of the 26 sound classes of the USM dataset. During playback, time-aligned visualizations of the audio signal’s waveform and Mel spectrogram were provided.

This also allowed participants to learn a visual association between different sound classes and their temporal-spectral characteristics. In the second step, 11 randomly chosen soundscapes were provided as examples each for

the polyphony degrees within $y_p \in [2, 6]$ in order to get familiar with the main annotation task. All sound examples used in the training phase were taken from the training set of the USM dataset.

4.4 Test Procedure

For the listening test, we randomly selected from the USM test a set of 90 test items, which included 15 random isolated stems (polyphony degree of 1) and 15 random soundscapes from each sound polyphony degree within $y_p \in [2, 6]$. From this collection, 15 test items were randomly assigned to each participant while ensuring a balanced distribution of polyphony degrees across all participants. In addition to the sound polyphony degree, the participants could annotate for each test item whether they felt certain or uncertain with their annotation. Furthermore, we constantly provided a list of all sound class labels during the annotation as reference. In total, each test item was annotated four times.

Inspired by [14], we considered three types of visual representations that were shown during the annotation. During the first group of five soundscapes, no additional visualization was shown. In the second group of five soundscapes, a waveform plot of the soundscape was shown. Finally, for the last group, a Mel spectrogram was shown.

4.5 Results

4.5.1 Influence of Annotation Certainty and Demographic Parameters.

We first investigate the dependency between the SPE performance of the listening test participants and the certainty of their annotations. Figure 4 shows in the left column the confusion matrices for SPE for all annotations (top) as well as separated between certain (middle) and uncertain (bottom) annotations. The right column shows histograms over the estimation error $\epsilon_p = \hat{y}_p - y_p$ with \hat{y}_p denoting the estimated polyphony degree. We first observe that only up to a polyphony degree of $y_p = 3$, the plurality of the corresponding annotations was correct. This result is in line with previous studies on similar auditory counting tasks as discussed in Section 1.1. When considering all annotations (top row), the polyphony degree is underestimated on average by $\bar{\epsilon}_p = -0.73$ (red vertical line). As a contrary trend, we found that in 31.5% of the uncertain annotations (bottom row), the sound polyphony was overestimated by $\epsilon_p = 1$.

When looking into other annotation parameters and user demographics, we found no significant correlations between the SPE performance with the age group of the participants (Pearson correlation coefficient of $\rho = -0.31$, $p > 0.05$) or the training time prior to the listening test ($\rho = -0.08$, $p > 0.05$). The type of soundscape visualization (no visualization, waveform, or Mel spectrogram) did not have a significant influence on the participants’ accuracy A_{SPE} as confirmed by a one-way ANOVA ($F(2, 69) = 0.05$, $p = 0.95$), and also by the direct feedback of the participants. These results stand in contrast to the findings from [14], where annotators perform better in

Fig. 4. Confusion matrices (left) and histograms over the polyphony degree prediction error ε_p (right) of listening test participants for all annotations (top) and separated by certain (middle) and uncertain (bottom) annotations. Thicker bounding boxes indicate the percentage of correct estimations per polyphony degree (main diagonal). In the histogram plots, the dashed lines show the average over ε_p and the dotted line indicates $\varepsilon_p = 0$.

SED when soundscapes were visualized as spectrograms. As mentioned in Section 4.2, we only asked the listening test participants if they had participated in listening tests in the past, but not to what extent they were already familiar with spectrograms. Participants confirmed that particularly noisy sounds, such as wind or car are difficult to detect and to count visually based on their spectrograms.

4.5.2 Influence of Sound Characteristics

In this section, we aim to investigate which types of sounds are harder to count in polyphonic soundscapes than others. Naturally, the sound polyphony annotations only relate to the number but not the type of audible sound classes. As a consequence, the relationship between SPE performance and the presence and absence of particular sound classes can only be investigated via an indirect approach.

In the following, $N_f \in \mathbb{N}^+$ denotes the total number of test files used in the listening test, $N_a \in \mathbb{N}^{N_f}$ denotes the number of annotations per file, $(\hat{y}_{p,f})_f \in \mathbb{N}^{(N_a)_f}$ for $f \in [1, N_f]$ denotes the sound polyphony annotations of file f , $y_{p,f} \in \mathbb{N}^{N_f}$ denotes the true sound polyphony per test file, and $y_{c,f} \in \{0, 1\}^{N_f \times N_c}$ denotes the sound class activity per file and sound class.

We first average over all annotations per file to compute a file-level (absolute) polyphony estimation error

Fig. 5. Class-level polyphony error $\varepsilon_{p,c}$ sorted in ascending order. Class names are extended by a categorization of their spectral pattern as harmonic (H), transient (T), or noisy (N). Lower values indicate better performance.

$\varepsilon_{p,f} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_f}$ as

$$(\varepsilon_{p,f})_f = \frac{1}{(N_a)_f} \sum_{a=1}^{(N_a)_f} |(\hat{y}_{p,f})_{f,a} - (y_{p,f})_f|. \quad (4)$$

Then, we compute a class-level polyphony error $\varepsilon_{p,c} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_c}$ as

$$(\varepsilon_{p,c})_c = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} (\varepsilon_{p,f})_f \cdot (y_{c,f})_{f,c} \quad (5)$$

for $c \in [1, N_c]$.

Based on manual inspections of several sound examples, we categorize the 26 sound classes of the USM dataset into harmonic (H), transient (T), and noise-like (N) sounds as shown in Figure 5. Then, we study how the number of active sound classes per category affect the file-level polyphony annotation error $\varepsilon_{p,f}$ for a given soundscape.

As a general trend, $\varepsilon_{p,f}$ increases with increasing polyphony degree y_p (Pearson correlation coefficient of $\rho = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$), which confirms that SPE becomes harder for soundscapes with higher polyphony. Interestingly, the number of noisy sound classes ($\rho = 0.62$, $p < 0.001$) followed by the number of transient sound classes ($\rho = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$) have the largest influence on the SPE performance. We conclude that due to their broadband spectral characteristics, sounds from these two sound class categories are harder to distinguish once they overlap. In contrast, the number of harmonic sound classes only shows a small correlation of $\rho = 0.24$ ($p < 0.01$)

with $\epsilon_{p,f}$. We conclude that concurrent harmonic sound events show a smaller amount of overlap due to their sparse energy distribution along frequency.

When looking at the class-level polyphony error $\epsilon_{p,c}$ shown in Figure 5, we observe that salient but rare sounds such as screams, church bells, sirens, and gunshots coincide with better polyphony estimation, whereas stationary sounds such as construction site sounds (e.g., drilling or jackhammer) correlate with worse performance. Surprisingly, although most familiar to human listeners, we observe high error values for speech and cheering. Nevertheless, we found that, contrary to the findings of [15] for SED, sparse sounds (H & T) are not easier to count than noise-like sounds (N), which is confirmed by a one-way ANOVA with no statistically significant difference in $\epsilon_{p,c}$ between both groups of sound class categories ($F(1, 24) = 1.06, p = 0.31$). Surprisingly, the smallest annotation error was observed for bird calls which are usually short and prominent in the mid to high frequency spectrum.

5 Machine Performance

5.1 Experimental Procedure

In our experiments, we evaluate three deep neural network architectures for SPE and SET. The architectures range from a small convolutional neural network (CNN) with 217k parameters [33], to the EfficientNetB0 architecture with 4.1M parameters [35], to the YOLOv7 model with 37.3M parameters [36].

The first two CNN variants described in Section 5.3 are trained for both explicit SPE and implicit SPE (compare Section 2). In the case of explicit SPE, each model is trained to predict the probability distribution $\hat{y}_p \in \mathbb{R}^6$ with $\hat{y}_p \in [0, 1]$ over all six sound polyphony classes using the categorical cross-entropy loss function. In the case of implicit SPE, the models are first trained for SET, i. e., to predict the individual probabilities $\hat{y}_c \in \mathbb{R}^{26}$ with $\hat{y}_c \in [0, 1]$ for all 26 sound classes using the binary cross-entropy loss function. Based on the SET results, the sound polyphony degree y_p is obtained by counting the detected sound classes with a probability of $\hat{y}_c > 0.5$. The training procedure used for the YOLOv7 models is detailed in Section 5.4. Here we only evaluate implicit SPE based on the predicted bounding boxes for a given Mel spectrogram.

5.2 Feature Extraction

Throughout our experiments, we represent monaural audio recordings sampled at 22.05 kHz with Mel spectrograms using a hop size of 441 (20 ms), an FFT size of 1024 (46.4 ms), and 128 Mel bands. We apply logarithmic magnitude scaling to reduce the overall dynamic range between salient foreground and subtle background sounds. As a final step, we normalize the Mel spectrograms to the range $[0, 1]$.

5.3 Convolutional Network Variants

The ‘‘VGG-like’’ (VGG) model was used for SED in [33]. It contains six convolutional layers with an increas-

ing number of filters from 32 to 128, a kernel size of 3×3 , and intermediate max pooling operations. Global mean and max pooling are applied to the final feature map and concatenated as input to the final two dense layers. The model size is 217k parameters.

We further included the Pretrained Audio Neural Network (PANN) embeddings [37] as they have achieved state-of-the-art performance for sound event tagging on the AudioSet dataset [38]. We used the pre-trained ‘‘CNN14’’ model, which is composed of 12 convolutional layers and two dense layers. The 512-dimensional embedding vectors are used as input for a simple two-layer multilayer perceptron (MLP model), which includes a dense layer with 128 neurons, a ReLU activation function, and a final dense layer for classification. The MLP model has around 66k trainable parameters.

The EfficientNet architectures [35] were derived by simultaneously scaling the width, depth, and resolution of existing CNN architectures using a fixed convolution coefficient as a power to three constant values, while satisfying network complexity constraints. In our experiments, we test the EfficientNetB0 architecture, which combines regular convolutional layers with seven mobile inverted bottleneck layers that combine depth-wise separable convolutions and residual connections [39]. We compare two model variants: The first variant (EffNet) is trained with random initial weights. The second variant (EffNet IN) is first pre-trained on the ImageNet [40] dataset for visual object recognition before all model layers are fine-tuned using the USM dataset.

Both CNN architectures were trained over 200 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001. During training, we apply grid distortion (as implemented in the Albumentations Python library [41]) and SpecAugment [42] as data augmentation techniques to increase the variability of the training data. Grid distortion applies random spatial distortion locally in different areas of an image while SpecAugment combines time and frequency masking. Both techniques are applied randomly with a probability of 0.5.

5.4 An Object Detection Approach

In computer vision, object detection algorithms localize objects by estimating a surrounding rectangular bounding box and the object category. In the audio domain, sound events exhibit characteristic patterns in time-frequency representations such as Mel spectrograms [10]. Unlike objects in natural images, these patterns are not necessarily invariant to operations such as scaling and shifting along frequency [43]. While natural objects typically have closed contours, sound events have very different temporal-spectral shapes, ranging from sparse distributions of harmonic or transient sounds to texture-like distributions of ambient noise without well-defined temporal or frequency boundaries. As a result, the concept of bounding boxes for sound events in spectrogram representations is often ill-defined and ambiguous.

Fig. 6. Example results of the automatic bounding box estimation for a soundscape with a polyphony degree of $y_p = 3$ (USM training set, 10025.wav). Log-magnitude scaled Mel spectrograms are shown for the 3 underlying audio stems of the sound classes gunshot (top left, solid lines), motorcycle (top right, dashed lines), and birds (bottom left, dotted lines), along with the mixture (bottom right).

Nevertheless, in addition to the convolutional network variants described in Section 5.3, we use the YOLOv7 object detection algorithm [36] to detect sound events in Mel spectrograms based on characteristic spectral patterns. The network architecture includes a combination of standard convolutional layers, depth-wise convolutional layers, and skip connections. In addition, YOLOv7 uses a multi-scale approach where images are processed at multiple scales to improve detection accuracy. The network is trained using a combination of the mean square error (MSE) loss, which penalizes bounding box coordinate estimation errors, and a loss term based on the intersection over union (IOU) metric, which penalizes the difference between the predicted and ground truth class labels. This combination of losses measures the localization and classification performance simultaneously. One key aspect of YOLOv7 is the use of anchor boxes with pre-defined aspect ratios that allow the network to detect objects of various sizes.

5.4.1 Automatic Bounding Box Estimation

As discussed in Section 3, the USM dataset provides only file-level sound class annotations without temporal boundaries of sound events [32]. Since a manual bounding box annotation is too time-consuming, we use an automatic approach to estimate bounding boxes for training the YOLO network. The USM dataset provides the underlying sound class stems for each soundscape. We therefore estimate bounding boxes from each individual stem and combine all stem-level bounding boxes as ground truth annotation for the soundscape. Each bounding box is described by the sound event onset time t_0 and offset time t_1 , the lower and upper frequency boundaries f_0 and f_1 , as well as the corresponding sound class y_c . We apply several methods provided by the OpenCV library [44].

Fig. 7. Two approaches for bounding box estimation based on time and frequency boundaries (YoloTF, left) and only temporal boundaries (YoloT, right). For illustration purpose, the colored rectangles indicate a subset of all sound events in the polyphonic example shown in Figure 1 including the sound classes dog barking (yellow dashed line) and drilling (green solid line).

We first compute a log-magnitude Mel spectrogram (see Section 5.2) and normalize it to a range of $[0, 255]$. We also upscale the resolution of the obtained “spectrogram image” from 128×216 to 640×640 using bicubic interpolation. A Gaussian blur low-pass filter with a kernel size of 7×7 is used to remove smaller artefacts.

Next, we binarize the spectrogram image to find contours which characterize the specific shape of sound event patterns in the Mel spectrogram. After initial experimentation, we decided to use a static binarization threshold of 127. We then use the `cv2.findContours` method to obtain a set of potential bounding box candidates from the binarized image. Finally, we refine this set and remove all bounding box candidates whose area is less than the mean area of all bounding box candidates. We have found empirically that this dynamic threshold leads to good results, as it removes many erroneous small bounding box candidates and also adapts to each individual spectrogram.

This automatic labelling procedure naturally introduces label noise, which we cannot quantify at this stage. We manually inspected around 50 training set files and found that the estimated bounding boxes were more reliable for sound classes with localized sounds such as dog barking, gunshots, and sirens, while the bounding boxes for ambient and noise-like sounds often spanned the entire time and frequency range.

This observation is illustrated in Figure 6 for a training set example with a sound polyphony degree of $y_p = 3$. The first three subplots (top row and bottom left) show the estimated bounding boxes for the three stems associated with the sound classes gunshot, motorcycle, and birds, while the fourth plot (bottom right) shows the combination of all bounding boxes as annotation for the soundscape. The estimated bounding boxes for the noise-like motorcycle (dashed lines) and gunshot (solid line) sounds do not capture particular patterns but instead cover the full frequency and time extent. In contrast, the bounding boxes estimated from the bird recording well capture individual occurrences of the recurring bird call pattern (dotted lines).

5.4.2 Bounding Box Strategies

In our study, we adapt the YOLOv7 network for implicit SPE and first predict bounding boxes for individual sound

Table 1. Method overview for SPE including the applied deep neural network architecture (second column), pre-training dataset (third column), and number of parameters (fourth column). Results are shown for implicit and explicit SPE based on the SET metric mAP_{SET} as well as the accuracy scores A_{SPE}^{Impl} and A_{SPE}^{Expl} . \uparrow Upper bound A_{SPE}^{Impl} value using optimal class-wise thresholds is shown for best-performing model *EffNetIN*. Best results are shown in bold print.

Label	Network Architecture	Pre-trained on	Trainable Parameters	Implicit SPE		Explicit SPE
				mAP_{SET}	A_{SPE}^{Impl}	A_{SPE}^{Expl}
VGG	VGG-like CNN [33]	-	217k	0.38	0.10	0.36
PANN	PANN [37] + MLP	AudioSet [38]	66k	0.41	0.16	0.31
<i>EffNet</i>	EfficientNetB0 [35]	-	4.1M	0.35	0.17	0.36
<i>EffNetIN</i>	EfficientNetB0 [35]	ImageNet [40]	4.1M	0.44	0.19 (0.27 \uparrow)	0.41
<i>YOloTF</i>	YOLOv7 [36]	COCO [45]	37.3M	0.29	0.30	-
<i>YOloT</i>	YOLOv7 [36]	COCO [45]	37.3M	0.23	0.15	-
Humans	-	-	-	-	0.31	-

Fig. 8. SPE confusion matrices that contrast human performance with the best algorithm performance in explicit SPE obtained by the *EffNetIN* model (compare Table 1).

events in a given Mel spectrogram and then estimate the sound polyphony degree y_p from the number of unique sound classes. Unlike bounding box estimation, SED algorithms only localize sound events in time. Therefore, we compare two bounding box strategies as shown in Figure 7: The *YOloTF* configuration considers the bounding box estimation over time and frequency while the *YOloT* considers only the temporal localization of each sound event, similar to SED.

5.4.3 Network Training & Fine-Tuning

The YOLOv7 network used for the *YOloT* and *YOloTF* algorithms was pre-trained on the COCO (Common Objects in Context) dataset [45]. The COCO dataset is a widely-used benchmark dataset for object detection, segmentation, and image captioning. It contains over 330k images with 80 object categories and over 2.5 million object instances.

After its pre-training, the YOLO-based networks were fine-tuned on the USM training dataset based on Mel spectrogram “images” combined with bounding boxes estimated using the procedure described in Section 5.4.1. The networks were trained over 100 epochs with a batch size of 8 images per batch. As the only difference, we extended the frequency limits of all the bounding boxes used to train

Fig. 9. Class-wise average precision scores for the *YOloTF* network for SET. Noise-like, transient, and harmonic sounds visualized using the same hatch encoding as before in Figure 5. Higher values indicate better performance.

the *YOloT* algorithm to the full frequency range of the Mel spectrogram.

6 Results

Table 1 summarizes the performance of all methods for implicit and explicit SPE. As evaluation metrics, we report the SET performance using the mean average precision mAP_{SET} over all 26 sound classes in the USM dataset and the SPE performance using the balanced accuracy scores A_{SPE}^{Expl} and A_{SPE}^{Impl} for explicit and implicit SPE, respectively.

The human SPE performance is provided as reference in the last row. We categorize the human performance as implicit SPE since all participants confirmed that they first tried to recognize sounds internally before counting them. Overall, the results demonstrate that SPE is very challenging for both humans and algorithms. The best-performing algorithms are the `EffNetIN` model achieving $A = 0.41$ for explicit SPE and the `YOLOTF` achieving $A = 0.30$ model for implicit SPE.

In general, explicit SPE seems to be the more promising strategy compared to implicit SPE. While the compared deep neural network architectures perform very well in pattern recognition tasks such as object detection in natural images, their performance in SET is still limited, as confirmed by the best mean average precision of $mAP = 0.44$ achieved by the `EffNetIN` model. We suspect that the number of remaining classification errors at this performance level is still too high to implicitly estimate sound polyphony based on the sound class predictions.

Figure 8 contrasts the SPE confusion matrices obtained from the listening test and the best-performing `EffNetIN` model. We observe that human listeners can estimate sound polyphony only up to a degree of $y_p = 3$ and perform poorly for higher polyphony degrees. In contrast, the `EffNetIN` model can distinguish better between soundscapes of higher polyphony degrees, which naturally also exhibit a stronger masking between different sound events. Most of the classifications errors happened between neighbouring classes even though the relationship was not explicitly modeled in the loss. This is in line with the results on speaker counting [19] and musical ensemble size classification [3].

In general, we observed low accuracy scores of the CNN variants for implicit SPE when using a fixed binarization threshold of 0.5 (see Section 5.1). To determine an upper bound, we examine the best-performing model `EffNetIN` and compute from the test set the optimal decision thresholds for each sound class that maximize the class-level f1 scores. These thresholds represent a hypothetical best-case scenario, since in common evaluation protocols the test set cannot be used for hyperparameter optimization. By using these class-level thresholds, the $A_{\text{SPE}}^{\text{Impl}}$ metric improves by 8 percent points from 0.19 to 0.27, which is still lower than the explicit SPE accuracy $A_{\text{SPE}}^{\text{Expl}} = 0.41$.

As shown by the `EffNetIN` model, pre-training on the ImageNet dataset is advantageous for SPE and SET, as the network can initially learn to recognize general two-dimensional patterns and then transfer and fine-tune this skill towards spectral patterns of different sound classes or polyphony levels. The `PANN` model is based on deep audio embeddings that are pre-trained on the AudioSet dataset. However, in contrast to the `EffNetIN` model, only the 66k parameters of the last MLP layers can be trained. Presumably, the significantly larger number of trainable parameters (4.1M) allows the `EffNetIN` model to better fit the USM dataset.

Table 1 also shows that the CNN-based models outperform the `YOLOv7`-based models in SET. This supports the

hypothesis that the bounding box concept is ill-defined for many sound classes, which is a key difference to objects in natural images. The annotation errors introduced by the automatic labeling described in 5.4.1 might be another reason for the performance difference. Comparing the `YOLOTF` with the `YOLOv7` network, we find that the former’s ability to localize sounds not only in time but also in frequency leads to an improvement in both SET and SPE performance. When looking at the class-level SET performance of the `YOLOTF` model shown in Figure 9, we observe that transient sounds such as drilling, hammer, dog barking, and gunshots on average are recognized best, followed by harmonic sounds such as sirens and speech, while it performs worst on noise-like sounds such as motorcycle and train. Particularly for noisy sounds, we observe different tendencies when comparing the human and machine performance on classifying and counting different sound classes. Most vehicle classes (car, truck, bus, train, airplane) and wind mostly have noise-like spectra, which are practically impossible to detect for the `YOLOTF` model. Showing an average precision value of around 0.4, sawing seems to be an exception, as it often includes repetitive sound components. When comparing these tendencies to the human class-level SPE performance in Figure 5, we assume that mainly the familiarity of listeners with particular sounds affects their ability to count them within mixtures of multiple sounds.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we studied the task of estimating the sound polyphony of complex soundscapes, which we define as the number of audible sound classes. We first reviewed scientific studies on both the human and machine performance in related auditory counting tasks such as instrument counting and speaker counting. In order to assess the human SPE performance, we carried out a listening test and studied in particular how the spectral characteristics of sound classes affect the human ability to count them. In turn, we evaluated deep neural network architectures of different complexities for the SPE task, which we approach both explicitly by directly estimating the sound polyphony as well as implicitly by first classifying the presence of each type of sound before counting them. As an alternative approach for sound classification, we adapted a state-of-the-art computer vision algorithm for detecting objects in images.

Human listeners were able to reliably count up to three concurrent sound classes with the estimation error further increasing with increasing sound polyphony. In particular for soundscapes with a polyphony degree of up to 3, listeners tended to underestimate the sound polyphony for annotations judged to be certain and overestimated the sound polyphony for uncertain annotations. Neither the age group, duration of the training phase, nor the type of audio visualization showed a significant influence on the SPE performance. Looking at the characteristics of the sounds, we found that salient but infrequent sounds are the easiest to count, presumably because they attract more attention.

The counting task becomes particularly challenging when several noise-like and transient sound classes overlap.

By combining pre-training using the ImageNet dataset with explicit SPE, the EffNetIN model could outperform the human listeners by 0.1 in accuracy and better distinguish between soundscapes of different sound polyphony degrees. While implicit SPE does not seem to be feasible with the investigated neural network architectures, explicit SPE seems to be more promising. In general, our results confirm that sound classes with sparse spectral energy distribution over time (transient sounds) and frequency (harmonic sounds) are easier to classify by machine listening algorithms due to clearly pronounced spectral patterns.

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